

QUALITY LIFE FOR THE FUTURE: DREAMS AND ASPIRATIONS OF PARENTS IN THE POVERTY LINE

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Abstract. This study extracted the dreams and aspirations of elementary parents in the pursuit of quality of life of the elementary pupils in Maa District, Davao City. There were eight (8) elementary school parents who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas from the participants. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the parents in the school. The virtual in-depth-interview was employed to gather information as regards to their respective experiences. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged as it relates to the dreams and aspirations of the participants: the dreams and aspiration of the parents for their children were on educating their children, being healthy and happy and develop life skills for the future. The coping mechanisms of the parents were: Keeping oneself strong, being resilient and being a practical home manager. The educational management insights of the parents were: thinking positive most of the time and looking at the brighter side family situation. The elementary teachers may give their full support to the parent's dreams and aspirations. Many of these learners may not be able to pursue their degrees, but they are being hired to work in a company, therefore it the teacher's role to redirect their students to a much better and fruitful way of life. The parents may be given proper information and guidelines on the new school policies. The parents play an important role in educating their children disregarding their current financial challenges. They too deserved to be resilient, happy and strong. The learners may be directed well through the constant reminders of their class advisers. Their performance at school depends on their clear understanding and application of their subject matter.

KEY WORDS

1. Quality life 2. Future 3. dreams and aspirations 4. Parents

1. Introduction

Parents dream big for the future of their children. No parent would dream bad for their children. Regardless of the economic status of each parent, they would always wish for the best in the future. Being a citizen of a developing country, each parent had been working so hard to make their financial capabilities able to support their family. As a parent that belongs to a poverty-stricken family, they strive to give the best to their children at their own capacity. What might be meager for other families, may be more than enough for another family. Every parent's dream was for their children to have quality life in the near future. Quality education has always been a priority for UNESCO. Now, however, attention to the concept of quality education has come to the fore as learners, parents and communities, educators, leaders and

nations acknowledge that what is learned and how learning occurs are as important as access to education. The age-old problems that have plagued educational quality remain, and are further complicated by new challenges such as the role of education in relation to sustainable development, peace and security, and the HIV/AIDS , pandemic, for example. (UNESCO, 2003). Education status plays a significant role in promoting quality of life in the short and long term. Some people think that education is limited to learn some subject to earn a certificate, They are narrow-minded. However, education is life; it includes every aspect of life, and its main role is to improve our lives. Education is essential to increase your opportunities to get a job. Gaining a university degree will double your chances to be hired, when you have good skills, you will enhance your resume. So, whatever you learn will contribute to your growth as a job seeker. As life never stops, people should never stop learning because learning new skills boarded your horizons. It opens and creates you new opportunities. You might not be satisfied with your first career choice, but there is always a choice to learn what you love and start a new career (Andry, 2018). Michalos (2008) emphasized that education, directly and indirectly, influences human wellbeing. Education enhances happiness and quality of life. Education has only a small direct effect on happiness. Education reduces poverty and income inequality, which in turn improves human wellbeing. This means that education increases chances of life success; thus, it also impacts quality of life . Education directly influences occupational status in the economy, thus improving the overall quality of life. The theoretical literature also considers that education is a key pillar of human health and wellbeing. Powdthavee (2010) postulated that many educators favor public support for education on the premise that education improves the overall quality of life of citizens. However, relatively little is known about the mechanisms

and the relative impacts of these different mechanisms through which more education actually contributes to people's overall life satisfaction. While income is naturally viewed as the main mediating factor of education on a person's wellbeing, many scholars have argued that education plays a much more important role in influencing individual's life satisfaction through non-monetary channels than through its impact on one's financial status. The critical need everywhere in the world is for education to prepare students to lead successful, fulfilling lives. In today's world, this means providing them with relevant educational experiences that nurture their passions, problem-solving abilities, and higher-level thinking skills, including critical thinking and creativity. The best solutions involve teachers, students, schools, and whole communities. In the U.S. and other Western democracies, commitment to a pervasive system of public education has gone hand-in-hand with growth and prosperity. Since the mid-19th century, mass public education has provided a foundation for millions of people to create a life for themselves and their families and to become actively engaged citizens. Today, in the developed world, we take for granted that children start school around the age of five and go through about 11 years of compulsory schooling (The Human Journey, 2023). In today's knowledge economy, an applicant with more education is more likely to be employed and land a job that provides health-promoting benefits such as health insurance, paid leave, and retirement.⁵ Conversely, people with less education are more likely to work in high-risk occupations with few benefits. The Socioeconomic status and education of an individual are said to be highly-related to future quality of life. Within the Philippines, the 2018 statistics have reported that the number of families living below the poverty line (Palmes et al 2021). Gumarang and Gumarang (2021) elucidated that education has a great role on the growth and development of

economy. It builds the young generation to become competent and future leaders of a country. It is observed by the Filipino people that there are problems in the Philippine education. There were three major problems in the Philippine education system such as overcrowded students in a classroom, teacher is teaching subjects that is not their expertise, and poor quality in instruction. Filipino parents value education as one of the most important legacies they can impart to their children. They believe that having a better education opens opportunities that would ensure a good future and eventually lift them out of poverty. Thus, they are willing to make enormous sacrifices to send their children to school. However, with a poor family's severely limited resources, education tends to be less prioritized over more basic needs such as food and shelter.

Hence, the chances of the family to move out of poverty are unlikely. It is therefore, important that the poor be given equitable access to education (LaRocque 2004). In the local scenario, particularly in Maa District, Davao City, I have observed that the parents were very eager to send their children to school. Noticeably, there were several parents who belongs to the poverty line. Despite their economic and financial status, they were focused on encouraging their children to go to school and learn. They have high hopes to a better life for their children in the future. They also believed that education is the key to a quality life. Further, as a researcher, I have observed that there is a meager information about the dreams and aspirations of parents for their children, thus, this study

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to explore the dreams and aspirations of the parents for their children. This study further explored the coping mechanisms of the parents as well as their insights about quality of life as a result of educating their children.

- (1) What are the dreams and aspirations of parents in the poverty line?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of parents to overcome life struggles as they aim to educate their children?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.2. Synthesis—The reviews gathered to support this current study focused on the quality of life of the learners in the future may be affected by their academic, social, political and economic experience. Literatures related to the dreams and aspirations of the parents were also cited in this study. Some cited significant lit-

eratures were also drawn from foreign experts in the discipline. Moreover, some literatures were cited as an output of the Philippine researchers in the field of education. Aside from the academicians who conducted in this field were coming from other European and American educations specialists

1.3. Theory—This study was anchored on Walberg's theory of educational productivity (1981). Walberg's theory sought to explain student performance. Being aware of the factors and variables that condition it, as these are clues as to why a student isn't reaching their full potential. That's why their grades don't

match their capabilities. Walberg's theory tackles about the influences on learning that affects the academic performance of a student. It is an exploration of academic achievement wherein Walberg used a variety of methods on how to identify the factors that affects the academic performance of a student. In his theory, he clas-

sified 11 influential domains of variables, 8 of them were affected by social-emotional influences namely, classroom management, parental support, student-teacher interactions, social-behavioral attributes, motivational-effective attributes. The variables are reflected with different representation. In the first three variables (ability, motivation, and age) reflect characteristics of the student. The fourth and fifth variables reflect instruction (quantity and quality), and the final four variables (classroom climate, home environment, peer group, and exposure to media) represent aspects of the psychological environment. He explained that these variables has a certain effects that might cause problems with the academic performance of students if it will not be properly guided. Giving importance with a certain variable can mean a big impact with the student's academic performance. This study was further anchored in the propositions of Ri'ayah Foundation (2019) this stated that the importance of education cannot be overestimated, as it is the key to a bright and successful future., it is our firm belief that all children deserve a chance to get a quality education, as it is the best way for them to realize their true potential. Our focus is to provide children with the opportunity to learn and develop, so they can grow up to be an integral and healthy part of their communities. Education is key to the healthy development of a people and their nation. Providing this to the children will ensure their future generations will have the opportunity to look towards a brighter future. This study was further anchored on the propositions of Lancersarmyschools.com (2023). They stressed that education is a key factor in the future of any individual. It is the key to success and prosperity. It helps people to achieve their goals and dreams. The role of primary education is to provide quality education to the students to develop their skills knowledge. It is also important for the parents to ensure that their children are getting a quality education. Quality education in primary schools also provides a good foundation for children to be able to learn more and excel in life. In order to ensure that all children who are eligible for education are able to attend school, we need to invest more in quality education at primary schools. The legal basis of this study were supported by the following laws and statements: In the Philippines, quality education is a pillar of national development. The 1987 Philippine Constitution guarantees the right to quality basic education. Aside from high budget allocation, the government continuously upscales the educational system to meet global standards. Despite substantial improvement in terms of access to basic education, the Philippines faced challenges in several areas of the educational system. Access to quality education is an issue with poverty being the strongest determinant (Maligalig et al, 2010). Children of families in the lower-income deciles and with less educated household heads are vulnerable and less likely to attend school. To address this concern, the Philippine government promulgated several laws such as Republic Act 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Law(Republic, 2012).

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assump-

tions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research – undertaking with the selection of the topic, problem or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm) meaning pattern, model for example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is an action of submitting to a view. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who defend a research paradigms a "basic set of belief that guide action", dealing with first principles, "ultimates" or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains on how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012) reality is a subjective and multiple as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realists exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the dreams and aspirations of the parents in reaching out a good life in the future was the main schema. In this study, I relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their

words and provided evidences of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure reliability of result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precludes from making personal bias as the study progress. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible as during the study in order obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985) as cited by Creswell (2013) state that on epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an “insider.” Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I will identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. The purpose of this research was to gather significant details on the dreams and aspirations of parents for their children to have quality life in the future, specifically those from Maa District, Davao City. I assured to establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that will shed light to the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on aspirations and and reams of parents for their children in the future. Axiology refers to role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes own interpretation in conjunction with interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and the value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. I

therefore preserve the merit of the participant’s answers and carefully interpreted the answers in the light of the participant’s personal interpretation. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in discussing the dreams and aspirations of parents especially for their children. As a researcher, I agree with the post modernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). I believe that the aims of education are teaching critical thinking, production of knowledge, development of individual and social identity, self-creation. In postmodern education teachers just lead students to discover new things. They provide opportunities to discuss about different subjects and make creative ways. In this situation student learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others criticism and try to think in critical way. They learn to respect other cultures and nationalities. Also they emphasize on cooperative learning independent learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It is deducted that postmodernism and creativity are embedded in each other and we can find the result of this opinion in postmodern education.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology is different from method. Methodology is creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study the challenges and coping mechanisms of parents in achieving their dreams and aspirations for their children were viewed. The parents coping ,mechanisms and their insights were also drawn to have a clear picture of their directions in life particularly those coming from Maa District, Davao City. The researcher’s drive in knowing the deeper meaning of the dreams as aspirations of parents became the basis for doing a qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and

Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena”. By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols and meaning of the experiences will be presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first is that experience is a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience is a source of knowledge and shapes one’s behavior. From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that “what” and the “how” (Moustakas, 1995),

2.4. Research Participants—The participants in this study were composed of eight (8) informants. The selected informants were the elementary school parents from the district of Maa, Davao City. All the participants were the elementary parents from various nearby schools. They must have been grossly involved in the school activities of their children in and outside the school, participated in various school programs. The participants must be coming from the poverty line family within the Barangay of Maa, Davao City. All the participants were coming from the elementary grade level, regardless of their age, sex and marital status. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample

the researcher projected that the subjective experiences and challenges of the parents and their insights were drawn as basis for the possible future researches and policy formulation and analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994). The data was then read and reread and culled for like phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation or experiences and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study phenomenology attempts to extract the most pure, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing is used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing (Maxwell, 2013).

sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25 and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. *Data Collection*—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process is to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they will provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data such as interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called “field issues,” which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the parents from Maa District, Davao City. Second is the access and rapport; letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student for the approval of the division superintendent; letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal and the concerned elementary teachers were prepared for easy collection of data. The third is the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were eight (8) informants selected in this study. The selected parents were considered group of individuals who can best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered as individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth is the recording procedures; the use of a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data; Davidson’s (1996) suggested the use of database in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. The COVID 19 Health Protocols. The data was collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time, therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (AITF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippines which was convened in January 2020. The Collection of data or the virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) was conducted following the protocols for Social Distancing which is one of the mandates of AITF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. In this study, the IDI was conducted with utmost care so that social distancing is followed and that at least 2 meters between persons was made. For some participants who missed the face-to-face social distancing efforts, the video-call via messenger, viber, zoom or google meet was used to gather the data or responses of the participants. The participants also filled-in the Interview Form provided to them and submit the same to the researcher.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of

the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it's a flexible method which can be both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is are interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyse documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other

methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation. The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations and other factors such as time, day, season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirements as mentioned is the use of environmental triangulation best suit the environment of the research being conducted.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and its answers based on the responses of the participants of the study. The parent participants revealed their dreams and aspirations for their children and families. This study also explored the coping mechanisms and insights of the parents specifically those who are currently enrolled in Maa District, Davao City.

3.1. Dreams And Aspirations Of Parents In The Poverty Line—

3.1.1. *Educate Their Children*—One of the aspirations of the parents in the school where I conducted the study was for their child to be properly educated. The parents were hopeful that their children can learn more knowledge and skills for their good life in the future. Most of the participants of this study talked about how they wanted their child to finish their elementary program and proceed to high school in the future and eventually finish their college education and find a good paying jobs in the

future.
3.1.2. *Being Healthy and Happy*—One of the themes that emerged from the personal interviews to the parents provided a significant theme. To be healthy and happy is everyone’s dream in life. No amount of money can buy health and happiness. Despite the current financial problems of the parents being interviewed in this study, they aspired for a healthy body, knowing that getting sick would mean money for the hospitalization and buying medicines. Despite being financially challenged, they wanted to be happy and learn to live their own present situation.

3.1.3. *Develop Life Skills for the Future*—The children need to be prepared for the future. That is one of the main objectives of schooling.

To learn basic life skills means a better working skill and earnings for the family. A skilled employee is much loved by their employers, this is a fact that we all know.

3.2. Coping Mechanisms Of Parents To Overcome Life Struggles As They Aim To Educate Their Children—

3.2.1. *Keeping Oneself Strong*—

Fig. 3. The Dreams And Aspirations Of Parents In The Poverty Line.

Being strong means being able to withstand most of the trials of these parents. One of their coping mechanisms was to keep themselves strong in terms of their physical health and will to live their kind of life situation. They were mostly poor families trying to send their children to school to be educated properly, not only learning the basic alphabet and lessons but to learn life skills.

3.2.2. Being Resilient—Being resilient also means being tough. Realizing that the life today is not easy as before, most of that participants of this study chose to be tough in terms of their health and will to survive. As currently bombarded with different problems like the daily family expenses, unexpected sickness, school contributions and other fees made their life more difficult. Thus, one of their coping mechanisms is to develop resilience against all those problems faced on a day-to-day survival.

3.2.3. Being A Practical Home Manager—As a home manager, the mothers are expected to be practical in many ways. For the parent participants of this study, being practical and wise in managing their homes saved a lot of money. Buying only the most important food and household needs made them save a lot of money. Being a wise consumer means they are able to make their finances go a long way. For food, for instance, they can buy cheaper but equally healthy vegetables and fish as sources of energy and protein. They cannot deny that they were all poverty laden as of the moment but they were very optimistic that they can get themselves out of the challenges of their time.

4. Look At The Brighter Side Of Family Situations

Despite their financial challenges, the participants of this study stood straight and considered the brighter side of their families. Deprived of so much money and good paying job, these families were resilient enough to stay where they are and strived to reach the destination they intend to aspire. For them, there are several factors that needs to be grateful about. Their simple lifestyles speak for their actions, simple and yet happily being with their families.

3.3. Educational Management Insights Drawn From The Participants Of The Study—

3.3.1. Think Positive Most Of The Time—For the participants of this study, thinking positively most of the time relieved them from the grueling forces of nature surrounding them.

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Drawn From The Participants Of The Study

4.1. *Implications*—In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to solicit the ideas of parents in terms of their dreams and aspirations for their children in the future. Their coping mechanisms were also drawn and some significant insights were also taken into account. This study was conducted in Maa District, Davao City. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Creswell’s (2006) guidelines in which open ended questions for interview were applied to extract authentic understanding of the participants experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own experiences or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which was about the dreams and aspirations of the parents for the quality of life of their children in the future. Based on the results of thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the dreams and aspiration of the parents for their children were on educating their children, being healthy and happy and develop life skills for the future. The coping mechanisms of the parents were: Keeping oneself strong, being resilient and being a practical home manager. The educational management insights of the parents were: thinking positive most of the time and looking at the brighter side family situation.

4.2. *Implications and Future Directions*— The experiences of elementary school parents as to their dreams and aspirations for the quality of life of their children were revealed from their personal participation during the conduct of this study in Maa District, Davao City. The revelations of the parent participants firstly delved into educating their children. As a Filipino family, dreaming to have a better future of their children is their main agenda in the family. Despite their current monetary problems, still, these parents were very supportive of their children’s endeavors in learning. These parents were all aware that having a good education ensures a better future since they can easily find a job with their academic qualifications. The second theme that emerged from the analysis of data showed their dreams of being healthy and happy. Being healthy means that they can comply with the requirements set by the schools or class advis-

ers of their children. For them, being contented with what they have as of the moment leads them to live simply and at the same time striving to have a good life in the future. The third theme that emerged was on developing life skills for the future. It is everybody's concern that proper development of life skills can bring prosperity to the workplace and their respective families. Life skills depends on the place and time where the person currently stays. Thus, there is a need to upkeep with the current life skills demands of the employers since almost everything surrounding each of us keeps changing, a reality beyond our control. Pertaining to coping mechanisms of the parents, there were three themes that emerged. These are, keeping oneself strong, being resilient and being practical home manager. Keeping oneself strong vastly helps any person. This is one of the coping mechanisms of the parents. This means that the stronger the persons physical, social and economic situation, the better is the quality of their life. Another significant coping mechanism of the parents was about being resilient. To be resilient means to be strong no matter what happens. They continued to keep themselves fit to the call of their duties. These parents learned to stand strong and alert on their own. The third coping mechanism obtained from the participants was about being a practical home manager. In today's demands, being a practical thinker and a home maker makes one survive as demanded by economic struggles of each family and the effects of rapid climate change that disrupts farming and other human activities. The insights drawn from the participants of this study resulted in the identification of two major thoughts namely: thinking positive most of the time. It cannot be denied that there were times when we do not think about it right. Being able to positively think about the

current situation or problem, the better was their life. Another insight drawn from the findings of the study was on looking at the Brighter side of family status. Against all odds, these families stayed strong and healthy. Realities in life exist whether we like or dislike it. It's just a matter of working for it and gaining expertise to do what ever is directed in the workplace.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. For the principals or school heads to be more practical minded while implementing the school policies well. Being able to keep up with the rapid changes in academic implementation, several changes had been instituted. The school head may be more practical in the implementation of new policies. The elementary teachers may give their full support to the parent's dreams and aspirations. Many of these learners may not be able to pursue their degrees, but they are being hired to work in a company, therefore it is the teacher's role to redirect their students to a much better and fruitful way of life. The parents may be given proper information and guidelines on the new school policies. The parents play an important role in educating their children disregarding their current financial challenges. They too deserved to be resilient, happy and strong. The learners may be directed well through the constant reminders of their class advisers. Their performance at school depends on their clear understanding and application of their subject matter. For the future researchers, similar studies may be conducted in other divisions or schools where the uniqueness of family life is observable. Researches pertaining to family's social, political, economic, religious and civic activities may further be explored.

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